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The Editor-in-Chief

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Religious Intolerance as a Predictor of Violent Behaviour Tendency among Ilorin Residents, Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines how religious intolerance predicts violent behaviour tendencies among residents of Ilorin, Nigeria. In the context of Nigeria's multi-religious landscape, Ilorin has faced ongoing tensions that subtly endanger social cohesion. Theoretically anchored in Social Identity Theory and the Frustration-Aggression Framework, this study investigates how rigid religious identification and perceived collective frustrations translate into aggressive propensities. Using a correlational research design, data were gathered from 392 respondents through structured questionnaires and analysed using Pearson correlation, t-test, and ANOVA. The results indicated a positive and statistically significant relationship between religious intolerance and violent behaviour tendency, suggesting that higher levels of intolerance are linked with increased propensities for harmful behaviours. While no significant gender differences were observed, educational qualification showed a significant influence, indicating that higher education may mitigate susceptibility to violent tendencies. The study emphasizes the urgent need for enhanced interfaith engagement, targeted peace education, and community-based dialogue structures to promote mutual respect and coexistence. These insights contribute to a deeper understanding of identity-driven conflicts in religiously diverse settings such as Ilorin.

Keywords: Religious intolerance, Violent behaviour, Social identity, Peacebuilding, Ilorin.

Introduction

Nigeria is a highly plural society, characterised by extensive ethnic diversity and the coexistence of Christianity, Islam, and indigenous religious traditions. While this diversity reflects cultural richness, it has also generated persistent social tensions, particularly along religious and ethnocultural lines. Since independence, the Nigerian state has struggled to manage these divisions, with recurring episodes of ethno-religious violence undermining social cohesion, national security, and sustainable development (Salawu, 2010; Jegede, 2019). In this context, violence remains a critical obstacle to peace, serving both as a manifestation of unresolved social grievances and as a catalyst for further instability.

From a social psychological perspective, violence is commonly understood as an extreme form of aggression intended to cause physical harm, injury, or destruction (Anderson & Bushman, 2002; Bushman & Huesmann, 2010). Beyond physical acts, violence also encompasses behaviours that threaten rights, dignity, and safety, often emerging from learned patterns that escalate from verbal hostility to physical confrontation (William, 2019). Within plural societies, such behaviours are frequently shaped by identity-based perceptions and group allegiances, making religion a particularly salient factor.

Religion occupies a central place in Nigerian social life, shaping moral values, social relations, and political interactions. Although religious affiliation has historically fostered community solidarity, it has also fuelled conflict when framed by exclusionary or superiority-based beliefs. Religious intolerance closely linked to religiocentrism reflects the perception that one's religious group is superior and that alternative beliefs are inferior or illegitimate (Ray & Doratis, 1972; Ntho-Ntho, 2016). When such perceptions become entrenched, interactions between groups are often characterised by suspicion, fear, and hostility, increasing the likelihood of aggressive or violent responses (Salawu, 2010). Intolerance thus operates not only as a social attitude but also as a psychological process that legitimises harm against perceived out-groups (Basem & Rami, 2020).

Ilorin, the capital of Kwara State, offers a distinctive case for examining these dynamics. Often described as a city of Muslim–Christian coexistence, Ilorin has nonetheless experienced recurrent episodes of religious tension over the past two decades. In 2001, a confrontation occurred in Ile-Apa, Ilorin, when a Christian procession was accused of disrespecting a nearby mosque. The disagreement quickly escalated into physical attacks, destruction of roadside stalls, and community-wide tension. Although local elders contained the conflict, it created

long-term mistrust between the two communities (Kwara State Peace Report, 2002). A dispute emerged in Offa Garage in 2013 when a Christian worship session was perceived as disrupting evening Ramadan prayers. The disagreement escalated into a neighbourhood confrontation before traditional leaders intervened. Scholars identify the event as reflecting deeper tensions over noise, timing, and religious coexistence in mixed communities (Ibrahim, 2014). The 2021 hijab controversy, involving Christian mission schools and Muslim parents, is one of the most documented cases of religious tension in Kwara State. Protests, school closures, and legal interventions followed government approval of hijab use in grant-aided schools. The crisis remains a central reference point in contemporary analyses of religion and education in Nigeria (Premium Times, 2021; Adewumi, 2022)

These tensions have frequently stemmed from everyday social interactions such as disputes over public preaching, religious processions, worship practices, and shared spaces in markets, schools, and neighbourhoods rather than organised extremism (Adeyemi, 2008; Owolabi & Aremu, 2016; Yusuf & Hassan, 2020). While many incidents were locally contained, several escalated into physical confrontations, property damage, heightened insecurity, and prolonged intergroup mistrust (Olatunji & Ajani, 2011; Daily Trust, 2022). More recently, the extension of religious contestation into digital spaces has intensified youth-level confrontations, further blurring the boundary between online hostility and offline violence (Adebayo, 2023).

Taken together, these patterns suggest that even in relatively stable urban contexts, subtle and persistent forms of religious intolerance may contribute to behavioural tendencies that support or normalise violence. However, empirical studies that systematically examine how religious intolerance predicts violent behaviour at the individual level, particularly within Ilorin, remain limited. Guided by Social Identity Theory, this study therefore seeks to examine the extent to which religious intolerance predicts violent behaviour tendency among residents of Ilorin, while also exploring gender differences and the influence of educational qualifications. By foregrounding the psychological dimensions of intolerance and violence, the study contributes to peace psychology by highlighting how everyday identity-based attitudes can either undermine or sustain peaceful coexistence.

Empirical Studies

Religious Intolerance and Violent Behaviour Tendency

Research indicates that religious intolerance can drive aggressive or violent behaviour. National studies have linked intolerance to heightened social tension, interpersonal conflicts,

and, in extreme cases, communal violence (Oyeleye & Belo, 2022; Izuegbu & Obiefuna, 2024). While most work focuses on states with pronounced religious conflict, such as Kaduna, Plateau, Sokoto, and Borno, less attention has been given to relatively peaceful yet religiously diverse areas like Ilorin. This suggests that even in lower-conflict settings, intolerance may subtly increase the likelihood of violent behaviour, underscoring the importance of examining these dynamics locally.

Gender and Violent Behaviour Tendency. Findings on gender and violent behaviour are mixed. Some studies report that males are more prone to aggression, often shaped by socialisation and cultural norms, whereas others find no significant gender differences (Aidonojie, Ismaila, & Obieshi, 2025; Ezeudu & Saadu, 2025). In Nigeria, responses to intergroup tension may also be influenced by age, education, and exposure to diverse communities. Understanding these patterns is critical for assessing whether violent behaviour tendencies vary by gender in Ilorin and for developing inclusive interventions that target both males and females.

Educational Qualification and Violent Behaviour Tendency.

Education is widely recognised as a buffer against aggression driven by intolerance. Individuals with a higher level of education tend to show greater empathy, critical reflection, and restraint in response to perceived threats (Oyeleye & Belo, 2022). Research shows that formal education and community learning programs can foster tolerance, conflict-resolution skills, and awareness of religious diversity, reducing violent behaviour tendencies. These findings align with the current study, suggesting that higher educational attainment may mitigate the propensity for aggression in religiously plural communities like Ilorin.

Theoretical Framework

This study draws on social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979) and the frustration–aggression framework (Dollard et al., 1939) to explain how perceived threats to religious identity can foster antagonism toward out-groups. Religious intolerance is conceptualised as the independent variable, encompassing attitudes and behaviours that deny the legitimacy of differing religious beliefs and practices. Violent behaviour tendencies are treated as the outcome variable, referring to predispositions toward aggression, intimidation, or property destruction. The framework proposes that heightened religious intolerance is associated with greater violent behaviour tendencies, particularly in plural social settings where intergroup

contact is routine. Gender and educational qualification are included as socio-demographic factors that may condition how intolerance is experienced and expressed within peacebuilding contexts. Guided by this framework, this study aims to examine the extent to which religious intolerance predicts violent behaviour tendency among residents of Ilorin, Kwara State. Specifically, it investigates (a) the relationship between religious intolerance and violent behaviour tendency, (b) gender differences in violent behaviour tendency, and (c) the influence of educational qualification on violent behaviour tendency, and generates context-specific evidence to inform peacebuilding strategies and strengthen interfaith harmony in Ilorin and similar multicultural communities.

Methodology

Design and Procedure

A non-experimental correlational design was employed to examine the relationship between religious intolerance and violent behaviour tendencies. The study involved a single group of participants, with variables observed in their natural social settings. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to residents of Ilorin, Kwara State. Participation was voluntary, and responses were anonymous.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study population comprised male and female residents of Ilorin across age groups. Ilorin has an estimated population of approximately 974,000, based on projections from Nigeria's 2006 national census as reported by City-Fact (2019). A non-probability sampling technique was used. Taro Yamane's formula was used to determine the sample size, resulting in a sample of 392 respondents.

Measures

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire measuring religious intolerance and violent behaviour tendencies. Items were rated on a Likert-type scale. Religious intolerance items assessed attitudes toward other religious groups and acceptance of differing beliefs, while violent behaviour items measured predispositions toward aggressive or harmful actions. Higher scores indicated higher levels of each construct.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analysed using Pearson's correlation to examine relationships between variables. Independent samples t-tests and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to assess differences by gender and educational qualification. All analyses were conducted at a significance level of $p < .05$.

Taro Yamane's formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where ($e = 0.05$ level of significance, $N =$ Total population; $n =$ Desired sample) Substituting

$N = 974,000$; $e = 0.05$; $1 =$ Constant

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{974,000}{1 + 974,000(0.05)^2} \\ &= 399.84 = 400 \text{ (by approximation)} \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, a sample of 400 participants was selected. All gave informed consent and were aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. Confidentiality of responses was assured. After excluding incomplete questionnaires, data from 392 participants were analysed using SPSS 21.0 via a Pearson multiple linear regression analysis.

Results

Demographic data

This section shows the results of the data collected from respondents, presented in frequency counts and percentages.

Table 1: Demographic Information

Demographic Information	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	226	57.7
Female	166	42.3
Total	392	100
Educational Qualification		
No formal education	29	7.4
SSCE	118	30.1
Diploma	51	13.0
Bachelor degree	142	36.2
Master degree	52	13.3
Total	392	100
Marital Status		
Single	251	64.0
Married	141	36.0
Total	392	100
Religion		
Christian	239	61.0
Islam	141	36.0
Others	12	3.0
Total	392	100
N		353
AGE		
Range		33
Mean		34.35
Standard Deviation		9.55

Source: Field survey (2023)

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents' demographic data. Based on gender, 58.3% of valid respondents were male, and 41.7% were female. This suggests that the study has a higher number of males than females. Based on the respondents' educational qualifications, it was observed that 7.4% of the valid respondents have no formal education, 30.1% hold SSCE, 13.0% have a Diploma, 36.2%. Most respondents have at least a Bachelor's degree, with 13.3% holding a master's degree, indicating a generally well-educated group. Regarding marital status, it is observed that most respondents are single, comprising 64.0% of the total valid responses, while the remaining 36.0% are married. The distribution of respondents' religion is also presented in the table above. It was observed that Christianity accounts for 61.0% and Islam for 36.0% of the total valid respondents, while 3.0% indicated others. This indicates that there were more Christian participants in the study than Muslims. Lastly, Table 1 also showed the

descriptive statistics of the distribution of age. The range of respondents' age is 33, while the mean age is approximately 34 years with a standard deviation of 9.55.

Table 2: Relationship between Religious Intolerance and Violent Behaviour Tendency

Items	N	r	Sig.	Remark
Religious intolerance				Significant
	392	0.61*	0.05	
Violent behaviour tendency				

Source: Field survey (2023)

Table 2 shows a correlation coefficient of 0.61, with a significance value of 0.000 at an alpha level of 0.05. This indicates a significant relationship between religious intolerance and violent behaviour tendency, as the significance value is below 0.05 ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Simple linear Regression Analysis of Religious Intolerance on Violence behaviour Tendency

Model	B	Std. Error	t-statistic	Sig.
Constant	2.969	0.081	36.767	0.01
Religious intolerance	0.619	0.055	-11.183	0.01

Table 3: The result of the simple linear regression analysis indicates that religious intolerance is a predictor of violent behaviour. The constant $\beta_0(2.969, p < 0.05)$, regression coefficient $\beta_1(0.251, p < 0.05)$. The result indicates that religious intolerance significantly predicted violent behaviour tendency, $\beta = .62, SE = .06, t = -11.18, p < .001$.

The magnitude of the regression coefficient indicates a substantial effect, suggesting that religious intolerance accounts for a meaningful proportion of the variance in violent behavioural tendencies among the study population. Overall, the findings demonstrate that religious intolerance is a significant predictor of violent behavioural tendencies, underscoring its relevance to understanding patterns of violence-related attitudes and behaviours.

Table 4: t-test of the difference between males and females on violent behaviour tendency

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	Crit. t-value	p-value
Male	226	1.68	0.82	371	-1.13	0.21
Female	166	1.70	0.11			

Source: Field survey (2023)

As presented in Table 3, the t-value was -1.103, with a significance level of 0.271 at an alpha of 0.05. This indicates no significant difference in violent behaviour tendencies between males and females. The reason is that the significance value (0.271) exceeds the 0.05 threshold ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5. Analysis of Variance: Showing the educational qualification on the tendency towards violent behaviour

Source	df	SS	Mean Square	Crit. F-value	p-value
Between Groups	14	2.022	0.506	15.413	0.000
Within Groups	378	12.138	0.033		
Total	392	14.160			

Field survey (2023)

Table 6: Showing Scheffe's post hoc analysis of educational qualifications on violence behaviour tendency

Variable	x	SD	1	2	3	4	5
NO formal Education	1.56	0.02					
SSCE	1.75	0.29	0.19*	-			
Diploma	1.71	0.09	0.15*	0.03	-		
Bachelor Degree	1.63	0.08	0.07	0.12*	0.09		
Master Degree	1.81	0.14	0.25*	0.07	0.10	0.19*	

Source: Field survey (2023)

The post-hoc analysis in Table 6 revealed that respondents with master's degree ($M=1.81$; $SD=0.14$, $p<.01$) demonstrated a significantly higher mean score on violence behaviour tendency when compared to respondents with SSCE ($M=1.75$; $SD=0.29$, $p<.01$), Diploma ($M=1.71$; $SD=0.09$, $p<.05$) and those whom possess a bachelor's degree ($M=1.63$; $SD=0.08$, $p<.01$). Overall, the findings suggests that the level of educational qualifications is associated

with differences in reported violence behaviour tendency, with individuals with master's degree reporting the highest levels.

Discussion

The study investigated religious intolerance as a predictor of violent behaviour tendency among the Ilorin residents of Kwara state, Nigeria. The analysis of the result revealed that: There is a positive and statistically significant relationship between religious intolerance and violent behaviour in the studied population. This aligns with social identity theory, where Sterkens and Anthony (2008:35) observed that religions often promote religiocentrism by establishing their own identity. Religio-centrism combines positive attitudes toward one's in-group with negative views of out-groups; sometimes, it also involves sentiments of exclusiveness, believing one should favour one's own religion over others (Ray & Doratis, 1971, p. 170; Cahyo, 2015). Such attitudes often lead to exclusion, discrimination, and viewing one's group as superior, which can result in violence. Igboin's (2016) research on religious tolerance supports these findings, emphasising that intolerance is rejected in favour of tolerance because it encourages better relationships in a diverse society. The link between religious intolerance and violence is further echoed by Joseph (2013), who studied how religious diversity and intolerance influence civil conflicts. Using a religion tree to show relationships among faiths and measuring religious diversity at three levels, they found that both diversity and intolerance are significant predictors of conflict.

Another finding indicated that there is no significant difference between males and females in their tendency towards violent behaviour. This suggests that both genders have a similar likelihood of engaging in violent acts depending on the context, although the average indicates females may have a slightly higher tendency. This aligns with studies by Cote (2002), Siegel et al. (2006), and Sherrer (2008), which found that sex is a structural factor related to 'gender' that influences differences in socialisation, cognitive processes, and personality, thereby affecting various behaviours. It also supports the conclusion from Amornthip (2013) that, over the past two decades, females have demonstrated increased violence in terms of both frequency and severity, indicating that female violence is not markedly different from male violence. As a result, sex likely functions as a moderator in youth violent behaviour, linked to family responsibilities and influencing psychological traits such as personality, attitude, and values. Lastly, educational qualification significantly influences tendencies towards violent behaviour. This influence stems from the fact that individuals with higher education possess greater behavioural reasoning, both morally and contextually. Such reasoning helps them to refrain

from engaging in any form of violence. Achunike (2008: 287) previously suggested that misconceptions about others' religion or faith, incorrect religious orientations, low literacy levels among religious followers, selfishness among religious leaders, widespread poverty, and government involvement in religious affairs are among the factors responsible for interreligious conflicts in Nigeria, which contribute to the findings of the present study. Dzurgba (2010) also supports this view, asserting that educational qualification and individual reasoning influence violent behaviour. He argued that only the absence of parochialism, chauvinism, bigotry, and fanaticism can foster an environment of religious tolerance, considering individual traits. While the extremes of these traits can be detrimental, it is important to recognise that individuals have the right to love their religion. Caution should be exercised regarding the attitudes of religious leaders, particularly those whose maturity is questionable. The findings align with Maruna and Copes (2004), who acknowledged that many academic theories suggest that individual psychological variables, such as inner reasoning, influence behaviour. They concluded that situational reasoning positively correlates with violent behaviour, whereas moral reasoning negatively correlates with violence and delinquency among those with higher educational attainment.

Conclusion

This study reveals a significant positive relationship between religious intolerance and violent behaviour tendencies, confirming that intolerance in religiously diverse communities contributes to conflict. Although no significant gender differences were observed, educational qualification emerged as a critical factor: individuals with higher levels of education exhibited lower tendencies toward violent behaviour. This highlights the role of education in shaping attitudes towards religious diversity and promoting peaceful coexistence. Strengthening access to formal education, integrating peace and tolerance programs into school curricula, and implementing community-based educational initiatives are therefore key strategies for reducing violent tendencies. Combined with policy interventions and interfaith dialogue, these measures can enhance social cohesion and mitigate identity-driven conflicts in communities such as Ilorin.

Recommendation

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

- I. The government should initiate a Ministry of Religion responsible for educating the public on issues of equity, religious freedom, tolerance, and promoting unity and love among people of different faiths.
- II. Christian and Muslim leaders in Nigeria need to continue engaging in dialogue, facilitate interfaith education, and actively encourage their followers to avoid violence, fostering social and economic progress in the country.
- III. Establishing dialogue and reconciliation centres at local, state, and regional levels across Nigeria is essential for addressing and resolving religious differences among various faith groups.
- IV. Educational authorities should expand access to formal education and integrate peacebuilding and religious tolerance programmes into school curricula at all levels. Additionally, community-based and adult education initiatives should be implemented to raise awareness, promote understanding of diverse religious practices, and foster peaceful coexistence.

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